

QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT OF SPECTRAL FIDELITY IN SENTINEL-2 DEEP RESOLUTION 3.0

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Abstract

The Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) algorithm has been applied to Sentinel-2 data to enhance the spatial resolution of satellite images. The quality of these products must be evaluated to ensure their reliability for future applications. A comparative analysis was conducted between original Sentinel-2 (S2) images and S2DR3-enhanced images using metrics such as Pearson Correlation, RMSE, SSIM, PSNR, ERGAS, and SAM. Additionally, spectral indices (NDVI, NDWI, NDBI) were calculated to verify consistency in typical remote sensing applications. The results indicated spectral and structural fidelity in the evaluated bands, ensuring the validity of indices and quantitative analyses, provided that the method's limitations are considered, especially in applications requiring high spatial accuracy.

1 Introduction

Image enhancement through artificial intelligence (AI) is a process that uses machine learning algorithms, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs), to improve the quality of images, making them more detailed than would be possible with traditional processing techniques. One of the main types of enhancement is super-resolution, which consists of artificially increasing the resolution of an image, that is, the amount of visible detail, with greater sharpness and clarity [5, 6]. The AI-based Single Image Super-Resolution (SISR) technique has been applied in remote sensing products, aiming to improve the spatial resolution of data obtained by satellites [8, 10]. An example of this is the Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) algorithm, which uses AI to convert images from the multispectral bands of the Sentinel-2 satellite, which originally have resolutions of 10 m, 20 m, or 60 m, to an approximate resolution of 1 meter per pixel [1].

Although artificially generated images with enhanced spatial resolution (i.e., smaller pixel size) may highlight details that would otherwise be hidden—such as small bodies of water, narrow roads, or fine vegetation patterns, caution is required in their interpretation. AI-based super-resolution is not equivalent to traditional methods such as pan-sharpening, which use a high-resolution panchromatic band to enhance multispectral bands [4]. In fact, the S2DR3 algorithm performs the entire inference process solely based on the original Sentinel-2 image, without the use of auxiliary images or reference data. Thus, the lack of real ground truth for full validation introduces a level of uncertainty. Moreover, because this is a machine learning-based method, there is always the possibility of generating details that do not accurately reflect reality [2]. Therefore, it remains necessary to carefully evaluate the types of applications for which this data is truly viable and their inherent limitations.

For that purpose, the present study aims at evaluating the quality of the products generated by the Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) algorithm, with a focus on the spectral behavior of the sensor bands. The objective is to assess the reliability of these data for different applications and use cases in remote sensing.

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2 Methodology

Images from the Sentinel-2 (S2) satellite covering a 16 km² area in Salinas da Margarida, a Brazilian municipality in the state of Bahia (latitude -12.88 , longitude -38.75) were selected due to its diverse land use and land cover such as native vegetation, urbanized areas and water bodies. An image acquired on April 26, 2025, with no cloud cover and processed at Level-2A was used in this study. Bands 2 (blue), 3 (green), and 4 (red) were selected, each with a spatial resolution of 10 meters. Additionally, Bands 8 (Near Infrared –NIR) and 11 (Shortwave Infrared –SWIR), with a spatial resolution of 20 meters, were also used. All bands have a radiometric resolution of 16 bits. The same image was enhanced using artificial intelligence (AI) techniques through the Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) algorithm, resulting in a spatial resolution of 1 meter (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location map showing the original Sentinel-2 imagery (10 m resolution) on the left and the AI-enhanced version (1 m resolution) on the right. Areas A, B, and C display zoomed-in views of different targets for resolution comparison. Image from April 26, 2025, MSI multispectral sensor, composition R4G3B2.

Since the images have different spatial resolutions, and to avoid bias in the analysis, the S2DR3 image was resized (downsampled) to 10 meters using bilinear interpolation. This ensured spatial compatibility with the original Sentinel-2 image, allowing for direct pixel-by-pixel comparison between the two products.

A spectral correlation analysis was performed between the corresponding bands of the original Sentinel-2 (S2) image and the resized S2DR3 image. Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was calculated for each band pair. For quantitative evaluation, the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) was calculated to measure the average difference between the pixel values of the original and enhanced images. Additionally, the

Structural Similarity Index (SSIM) was used to assess structural similarity, taking into account contrast, luminance, and structure, while the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) was applied to quantify the relationship between signal and noise in the image. The Erreur Relative Globale Adimensionnelle de Synthèse (ERGAS), a global relative error metric for multispectral images, and the Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM), which measures the spectral angle between the spectral vectors of corresponding pixels in two images, were calculated as multiband evaluation metrics [7, 9].

Finally, spectral indices were calculated for both images (S2 and S2DR3): the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (Eq. 1), the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI) (Eq. 2), and the Normalized Difference Built-up Index (NDBI) (Eq. 3). These indices were selected because they combine information from different wavelengths (bands) of the electromagnetic spectrum in remote sensing images, with each index highlighting specific features of the observed targets.

$$\text{NDVI} = (\text{NIR} - \text{Red}) / (\text{NIR} + \text{Red}) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{NDWI} = (\text{Green} - \text{NIR}) / (\text{Green} + \text{NIR}) \quad (2)$$

$$\text{NDBI} = (\text{SWIR} - \text{NIR}) / (\text{SWIR} + \text{NIR}) \quad (3)$$

3 Results and Discussion

The comparison metrics between the S2 and S2DR3 image bands (Table 1) indicate a high degree of spectral and structural fidelity in most of the evaluated bands. All bands exhibited a strong linear correlation between the products, with Pearson's r values greater than 0.98. The visible bands (B02–B04) and the near-infrared band (B08) showed high PSNR values (above 41 dB) and SSIM scores exceeding 0.97, indicating that the super-resolved image (S2DR3) effectively preserves the original structure and radiometric values. Band B11 (SWIR1), on the other hand, exhibited lower relative performance, with a high RMSE (143.55), a PSNR of 31.85 dB, and an SSIM of 0.9034, indicating reduced spectral preservation in the super-resolved image for this wavelength range.

The Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) value of 4.06° indicates similarity between the spectral profiles of the two images, so the spectral signatures are faithfully preserved in the S2DR3 product. However, the Erreur Relative Globale Adimensionnelle de Synthèse (ERGAS) of 103.37 indicates that there are significant differences in the spectral average between the images, which do not necessarily compromise visual quality, but should be taken into account in future applications of this product.

Table 1. Comparison metrics between the original Sentinel-2 image and the resized Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) image bands.

Band	Correlation	RMSE	PSNR (dB)	SSIM
B02 Blue	0.9904	61.9216	42.40	0.9896
B03 Green	0.9885	61.1954	42.62	0.9897
B04 Red	0.9968	46.5644	43.75	0.9889
B08 NIR	0.9992	51.5571	41.76	0.9723
B11 SWIR1	0.9929	143.5450	31.85	0.9034
Global Metrics	ERGAS:	103,37	SAM:	$4,06^\circ$

The AI-assisted resolution enhancement did not introduce distortions or biases into the original spectral data. However, when calculating various spectral indices and comparing the results between the products (Figure 2), notable differences are observed. In general, the products derived from S2DR3 tend to smooth extreme values of the spectral indices. The observed differences are primarily concentrated in regions containing water bodies (such as the ocean, rivers, flooded, and saline areas) and along feature edges or geometric transitions between landscape structures. Water bodies and transition areas (feature edges) are

particularly challenging to distinguish using remote sensing. This difficulty arises from both the optical properties of water, such as high radiation absorption at different bandwidths and low spectral contrast, and geometric factors, including the occurrence of spectral mixing at boundaries. In these transitional regions (e.g., between forest and water or between agricultural fields and rivers), pixels often capture mixed signals from multiple land cover types, making accurate classification into a single category difficult [3]. Therefore, even improvements in spatial resolution are insufficient to fully overcome these limitations, as they stem from the inherent physical characteristics of the observed targets.

For NDVI, the differences between the products (S2DR3–S2) are predominantly positive across most water-bearing regions. In other words, the S2DR3 product exhibits lower NDVI values in these areas compared to the original Sentinel-2 image. In contrast, the opposite trend is observed for NDWI, where the differences are generally negative, indicating that NDWI values are higher in the original Sentinel-2 (S2) image than in the S2DR3 product. The largest differences in indices were observed for NDBI, with values ranging from -2 to 2 (dimensionless). This may be attributed to the fact that NDBI is the only index among those considered that involves Band 11 (SWIR1), which exhibited the greatest variation between the S2 and S2DR3 products. While NDVI and NDWI are designed to highlight vegetation and water bodies, respectively, both the original and S2DR3 products satisfactorily achieve these objectives for the scene analyzed. For NDBI, which targets the identification of built-up areas, the S2DR3 product yielded more satisfactory results.

Figure 2. Spectral indices derived from Sentinel-2 and resized Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 imagery. Includes difference maps between the indices and corresponding histograms.

4 Conclusion

Artificial intelligence can be used to enhance spatial image resolution achieving satisfactory results; however, it must be applied with caution. The Sentinel-2 Deep Resolution 3.0 (S2DR3) algorithm preserves the spectral signatures of targets, ensuring that indices and quantitative analyses performed with these products remain valid. The super-resolution product visually enhances spatial details but does not replace data collected at a true 1-meter resolution. Moreover, since this method is driven by artificial intelligence, there is always the possibility that the model may generate details that do not correspond to reality. Therefore, further studies focusing on specific applications of this data (such as segmentation and classification) are necessary to ensure that the product is genuinely useful for the remote sensing community and not merely an improvement in visual appearance.

It's important to consider the specific limitations of this approach, especially in scientific contexts. Whenever possible, we recommend using sensor data (drones or satellites) with finer spatial resolution to validate and compare the results obtained by S2DR3. While temporal coincidence between acquisitions can be challenging, this validation is particularly feasible in consolidated urban areas, where dynamic land cover change occurs less frequently. Furthermore, additional studies specific to specific data applications (such as segmentation and classification) are needed to more comprehensively assess the potential of S2DR3 and ensure that the product is genuinely useful to the remote sensing community, not just a visual enhancement.

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